

A note on previous proofs for Wilson's RST algorithm

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Abstract

In random graph theory, Wilson's algorithm is a widely employed algorithm for generating, for a given finite connected undirected weighted graph G representing a reversible Markov chain, realizations of a random spanning tree (RST) of G according to a well-specified and desirable probability distribution. The proof of the distributional properties, originally given alongside the algorithm in (Wilson 1996), and repeated in multiple textbooks on the subject, appears to be incomplete, and this correspondence seeks to close the remaining gap.

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1 Current viewpoint in literature

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a finite connected undirected graph associated to a reversible Markov chain with transition probabilities $(p_{xy})_{(x,y) \in E}$, and edge weights $c((x, y)) = \mu(x) \cdot p_{xy}$, where $\mu(\cdot)$ is witnessing reversibility. Wilson's algorithm then is defined as follows¹: Choose an arbitrary vertex $r \in V$ and fix a vertex ordering on the remaining vertices V' , say $V = \{r\} \cup \{v_2, \dots, v_n\}$. Let $A_1 = \{r\}$, and set $E'_1 = \emptyset$. Starting with $i = 2$, perform repeatedly, incrementing i until n :

1. Choose an arbitrary vertex from $V \setminus A_{i-1}$, call it u_i , and perform a random walk $W^{[i]} := (u_i = \xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_L)$ starting from u_i according to the $(p_{xy})_{x,y}$ until it hits A_{i-1} for the first time. Let $W'^{[i]} := \text{LE}(W^{[i]})$ be the loop-erasure of $W^{[i]}$.
2. Set $E'_i := E'_{i-1} \cup E(W'^{[i]})$ and $A_i := A_{i-1} \cup V(W'^{[i]})$ where $V(W'^{[i]})$ and $E(W'^{[i]})$ denote

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¹It is stated here only a version with fixed root.

the vertices resp. edges covered by the path $W'^{[i]}$.

Then finally $T = (V, E'_n)$ is a directed spanning tree of G rooted at r . Since the choices of successor vertices in the random walks were random, the resulting tree is a random object.

In the literature, proofs for typically the following statement are given: ²

Theorem 1: The probability of obtaining from above algorithm for T the specific directed spanning tree t rooted at r is proportional to $\prod_{e \in t} p_e$.

(Below, we will always refer to *directed* trees without mentioning. The distribution and other results for the undirected tree derived from T will not be of concern here, for brevity.)

The theorem is proven, in Wilson and in many other text books, using the concept of fixing a set of stacks of instructions at each vertex (except r) in advance, that give rise to subgraphs, possibly containing cycles, of which the cycles are repeatedly removed via a procedure called 'cycle popping': ³

For fixed previously chosen root r :

- define for each $x \in V'$ a *random stack* $(Y_{x,\eta})_{\eta \in \mathbb{N}}$ of *allowed target vertices* (called 'moves' or 'instructions') observing the transition probabilities, i.e. $P(Y_{x,\eta} = y) = p_{xy}$ for all $\eta \in \mathbb{N}$. Different values of η are referred to as different *colours*. Later we will start to refer to them as *levels*. All values $Y_{x,\eta}$ for all x and all η are deemed jointly independent.

²See for example Theorem 4.1 in [LP16], pg 97, or the origin Theorem 1 in [Wil96]. Theorem 2.6 in [Gri18], pg 24, refers to the case of uniform transition probabilities.

³The description here diverts somewhat from the original, towards a version in which the stack of instructions is deemed remaining fixed.

- for a given tuple of colours η_i at vertices v_i ($i = 2 \dots n$), define the *visible graph* G'' , by $G'' = (V, E'')$, with $E'' = \{(v_i, Y_{v_i, \eta_i}), i = 2 \dots n\}$.
- call '*popping of a cycle*' the removal of a cycle from the visible graph, by generating the next visible graph by incrementing the η_i whose i correspond to cycle vertices.

When the procedure of repeatedly examining the currently visible graph, starting at colours $\eta_i = 1$ for all $i = 2 \dots n$, and subsequent popping of possibly existing cycles is performed, one may need to account for the possibility that multiple choices of sequences of cycle poppings may exist, in a given realization of stacks of moves. The outcome of the procedure after N cycle poppings, when N is taken to infinity or until ending with a cycle-free visible graph, thus *a priori* must be regarded as undetermined, even given a single stack realization. However, a lemma, used in Wilson [Wil96] (there called Theorem 4) and commonly used in the literature as a subcomponent for Theorem 1 (see for example [LP16], Lemma 4.2, pg 98; or [Gri18], Lemma 2.10, pg 27), states this is not the case. Concretely (and here citing verbatim from [Gri18]):

Lemma 1: The ordering of cycle popping is irrelevant to the outcome, in that:

- either $N = \infty$ for all orderings of cycle popping,
- or the total number N of popped cycles, and the output σ [here: = resulting visible graph], are independent of the order of popping.

The proof of this lemma is however, in each of the aforementioned sources, incomplete. More concretely:

- The proof of the lemma as given in (Grimmett 2018) [Gri18] only shows that any poppable cycle which is poppable *from the initial layer of the stacks* must be contained in the given sequence of cycle poppings. (A coloured cycle, somewhere located in 'later' layers, may exist which was not part of the firstly chosen cycle popping sequence.) The proof cannot be used to conclude that the output will be equal for all possible cycle poppings.

- The proof in [Wil96] of the equivalent of Lemma 1 does prove, similarly as in [Gri18], only that an *initially poppable* cycle is occurring in an arbitrary popping sequence. Only the argument for the coloured cycle equality is formulated differently.
- In [LP16], the statement "whereas in the alternative case every coloured cycle that can be popped will be popped" (pg 99 there) does not really follow from the previously given arguments in the same paragraph (there).

The remainder of the present correspondence is meant to address this gap. It will be seen (in proof of Lemma 2.1 below) that all major aspects of the argument have indeed been already present in the previously given proofs.

2 Full proof of the lemma for proving Wilson's theorem

In order to state the required proof, we will introduce a few new definitions⁴, which will allow us to arrive at proof length similar to the original one, while also enhancing clarity.

We again start from a fixed realization of stacks of moves $(Y_{x, \eta})_{x \in V', \eta \geq 1}$. For such realization, and the originally fixed enumeration $(v_i)_{i=2 \dots n}$ of nodes of V' , call

- a *graph state for G* the finite sequence $(\eta_1, \dots, \eta_n) =: \vec{\eta}$ (each η_i signifying the current *level* (or *read position*) in the respective stack of node v_i), and let the associated *visible graph* $G^{\vec{\eta}}$ be defined (in line with [Gri18]) as having the same vertex set as G and $(x, y) \in E^{\vec{\eta}} : \Leftrightarrow \exists i : x = v_i$ and $Y_{x, \eta_i} = y$. The visible graph is a directed graph, irrespective of whether G is directed or not.
- a sequence $(x_k, \tilde{\eta}_k)_{k=0 \dots L-1}$, with $\tilde{\eta}_k \geq 1$, a *coloured cycle*, if $(x_k)_{k=0 \dots L-1}$ is a cycle in G and $Y_{x_k, \tilde{\eta}_k} = x_{(k+1) \% L}$ for all k . Denote coloured cycles also by letters C , as done with "ordinary" cycles. Further denote $V(C) = \{x_k : i = 0 \dots L - 1\}$.
- a graph state $\vec{\eta}$ having a *visible cycle* if exists in $G^{\vec{\eta}}$ an (ordinary) cycle (say $(x_k)_{k=0 \dots L-1}$)

⁴In fact, the definitions of 'coloured cycle', 'visible graph' and 'cycle popping' semantically agree with the definitions used in existing literature.

(In that case $(x_k, \tilde{\eta}_k)_{k=0\dots L-1}$ is the corresponding coloured cycle.)

- for a graph state $\vec{\eta}$, the *popping of coloured cycle* C (only in as far as the corresponding ordinary cycle exists in $G^{\vec{\eta}}$) the procedure of obtaining a graph state $\vec{\eta}'$ from $\vec{\eta}$ which removes that cycle. As hinted in the previous section, $\vec{\eta} \mapsto \vec{\eta}' = \vec{\eta} + \vec{1}_{\{C\}}$ is that procedure, and one can refer with $(\vec{\eta}, \vec{1}_{\{C\}})$ to the corresponding *cycle popping*. (Here $\vec{1}_{\{C\}} = \sum_{i=2}^n 1_{v_i \in C} \cdot \vec{e}_i$ is like a vectorial cycle membership indicator.) A cycle popping may in fact be identified (i.e. is fully determined) by its coloured cycle.
- a *program for popping coloured cycle* C a sequence of cycle poppings $\pi := (C_1, \dots, C_L)$, which is in that order applicable starting from graph state $\vec{\eta} = \vec{1}$, and which has C as last cycle popped, i.e. $C_L = C$. (Below we use terminology 'admissible program' to stress that the cycle poppings prescribed must be indeed applicable.) The cycles C_j , $j = 1\dots L$, are deemed elements of the program; in symbol: $C_j \in \pi$.
- a program *terminal* if the associated ordinary graph of the resulting graph state has no (ordinary) cycles.
- a coloured cycle C *attainable* if there is a program for popping it. (Here we deviate from the original terminology, to reserve the property 'poppable' for being assigned to a specific graph state.) (As recognized elsewhere, in a given stack realization there can, in general, exist non-attainable coloured cycles.)

Based on the above definitions, we now state and prove a new lemma, which is a slight strengthening of the previously used lemmata. The proof of this lemma constitutes the main contribution of this text.

Lemma 2.1. *For any realization of stacks of moves, the initial graph state either permits cycle popping infinitely many times (irrespective of the sequence of poppings chosen), or each terminal program pops (/contains) exactly the same set of coloured cycles. Furthermore the resulting visible graph from applying any terminal program on the stack realization is the same.*

Proof. (using the abbreviation 'ccycle' for 'coloured cycle'.)

Consider first only the case that there exists a terminal popping program.

Let C be an attainable ccycle, and $\pi = (C_1, \dots, C_s = C)$ be the associated program, further $\tilde{\pi} = (\tilde{C}_1, \dots, \tilde{C}_m)$ be an arbitrary terminal program. Need to show⁵ that $C \in \tilde{\pi}$. Denote $\bigcup_{j=1..m} V(\tilde{C}_j) =: \tilde{B}$.

First determine the earliest ccycle in $\tilde{\pi}$ that has a common vertex with C_1 , i.e. obtain the $j \leq m$ such that $V(C_1) \cap V(\tilde{C}_j) \neq \emptyset$ and $V(C_1) \cap V(\tilde{C}_{j'}) = \emptyset$ for $j' < j$. (If such j did not exist, then $V(C_1) \cap \tilde{B} = \emptyset$, so C_1 applicable after program $\tilde{\pi}$, and so $\tilde{\pi}$ not a terminal program, counter to assumption.)

Therefore, there exists a smallest $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ with $V(C_1) \cap V(\tilde{C}_j) \neq \emptyset$. Since it was the smallest such j , at the shared vertex $x = v_{i_1}$ the instruction read comes from level $\eta_{i_1} = 1$, for both cycles. Thus the successor vertex of x is identical for both cycles. As argued in the previous proofs, examine now whether in \tilde{C}_j , the level of the second vertex could be larger than 1. If so, apparently C_1 and a $\tilde{C}_{j'}$ with $j' < j$ would share a vertex, counter to the choice of j . Thus at the second vertex the two ccycles again have equal instructions. Continuing one concludes that the two ccycles are identical. (Additionally we conclude that since $V(C_1)$ was disjoint from $V(\tilde{C}_1, \dots, \tilde{C}_{j-1})$, also $V(\tilde{C}_j)$ is disjoint from the latter vertex set. (*)) Set $j_1 := j$.

Denote by $\tilde{\pi}^{(1)}$ the program $(\tilde{C}_{j_1}, \tilde{C}_1, \dots, \tilde{C}_{j_1-1}, \tilde{C}_{j_1+1}, \dots, \tilde{C}_m)$ obtained by relocating \tilde{C}_{j_1} in $\tilde{\pi}$. We may regard the running of π and $\tilde{\pi}^{(1)}$ from $\vec{1}$ as running the corresponding reduced programs $\pi_{2:s}$ and $\tilde{\pi}_{2:m}^{(1)}$ from the same state $\vec{1} + \vec{1}_{\{C_1\}} = \vec{1} + \vec{1}_{\{\tilde{C}_j\}}$. Note that $\tilde{\pi}_{2:m}^{(1)}$ is admissible at that state because of (*). Repeating the same argument now on the reduced programs, one can determine that for C_2 there exists a ccycle \tilde{C}_{j_2} with some j_2 such that $C_2 = \tilde{C}_{j_2}$, and remove them when creating the next reduced program pair. Again the two reduced programs will find themselves (at start) situated at the same graph state. Since by previous argument, the $\tilde{\pi}$ cannot prematurely end in this process, there is eventually a j^* with $\tilde{C}_{j^*} = C_s = C$, proving the desired.

⁵And here the argument starts to differ from the ones in previous proofs.

Examine lastly the output of any two terminal programs. Firstly, by above arguments they have equal length N . Next, the repeated cycle re-ordering transformation applied to $\tilde{\pi}$, i.e. $\tilde{\pi} \mapsto (\tilde{C}_{j_1}, \tilde{C}_1, \tilde{C}_2, \dots) \mapsto \tilde{\pi}^{(2)} = (\tilde{C}_{j_1}, \tilde{C}_{j_2}, \tilde{C}_1, \dots) \mapsto \dots \mapsto \tilde{\pi}^{(N)}$ is seen to leave the output nevertheless invariant (because the single relocations only change sequence among vertex-disjoint cycle poppings). But since after N transformations the two resulting programs are identical, i.e. $\pi = \tilde{\pi}^{(N)}$, conclude $\pi(G) = \tilde{\pi}^{(N)}(G) = \tilde{\pi}(G)$.

Note: If a terminal program exists, then there can apparently be no indefinitely running program, since each cycle in the latter (by being an attainable cycle) must be contained in the former program.

Consider now the case where there exists an indefinitely running program. Then by previous paragraph there can be no terminal program based on the same stack realizations. Thus any program is indefinitely running, in that case. \square

(Only arguments of the 2nd and 3rd paragraph within the first case fully concur with previous proofs.)

For completeness, refocus now on the original theorem, Theorem 1 above. As first step, one notes that in the stack-based (sb) spanning tree generation, each specific final outcome t (upon termination) will occur with a probability proportional to $\prod_{(x,y) \in t} p_{xy}$. For this, consider the stack values Y_{\cdot} as random, and let (under event E of termination) $\vec{\eta}^*$ be the common graph state at which all programs end. (By above lemma, restricted to E all programs contain the same cycles, so the resulting sets of covered vertices (seen as multiset) of the cycles are identical.) Then apparently the spanning tree is fully determined by the values $Y_i^* := Y_{v_i, \eta_i^*}$, $i = 2 \dots n$, and because of the presumed joint independence the law of these values is independent of those outside of $\vec{\eta}^*$, in symbols $P(Y_{\cdot, \eta^*} = \vec{y} \mid Y_{\xi, \eta'}, (\xi, \eta') \neq (v_i, \eta_i^*) \forall i) = P(Y_{\cdot, \eta^*} = \vec{y})$. Note that the components of \vec{Y}^* are not independent. To proceed, consider a list of all possible values of \vec{y} , together with the probability that they occur when each component of \vec{y} were to be chosen independently according to probability $P(Y_i^* = y_j) = p_{v_i, y_j}$. Then $P_{indep}(\vec{Y}^* = \vec{y}) = \prod_{i=2}^n p_{v_i, y_i}$. The only restriction imposed on \vec{y} in the stack-based gen-

eration is that \vec{y} may not imply a cycle in $G^{\vec{\eta}^*}$, thus $P_{sb}(\cdot) = P_{indep}(\cdot \mid \text{no cycle from } \vec{y})$. It is evident that the conditioning on admissible \vec{y} does not change the ratios of probability of occurrence among the admissible \vec{y} . Thus $P_{sb}(\vec{Y}^* = \vec{y})$ is proportional to $\prod_{i=2}^n p_{v_i, y_i}$.

As a second step, it suffices that a specific run of Wilson's algorithm can be associated to a realization of stack variable values, up to and including $\vec{\eta}^*$, in a way such that the law of the occurring random variables matches. For this, one places the moves taken (from any vertex to root r or to the so far existing subtree), in that order on the stacks, with η_i always set to one plus the previous visit count at the respective vertex. (This procedure cannot yield any possible stack realization, since the attainable cycles so obtained must always be vertex-disjoint across new path starts.) Let \mathcal{A}_w be the set of all programs realizable by this association to Wilson's algorithm. Then still $P_w(T = t) = \sum_{\pi \in \mathcal{A}_w} P_w(T = t, \Pi = \pi) = \sum_{\pi \in \mathcal{A}_w} P_{sb}(T = t \mid \Pi = \pi) \cdot P_{sb}(\Pi = \pi) = \sum_{\pi \in \mathcal{A}_w} P_{sb}(T = t) \cdot P(\Pi = \pi) = P_{sb}(T = t) \cdot \text{const}$, i.e. again crucial is that the restriction to a subset of all programs does not change relative probabilities.

3 Acknowledgements

The (new) arguments presented in this text were conceived after seeing a presentation along the lines of [Gri18].

References

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